

Association of Total Serum Creatine Kinase in Patients Presented with Seizures and Epilepsy**Nikita Yadav¹, Sonika Choudhary², Tarun Ralot³, Alka Choudhary⁴, Pooja Kumawat⁵**¹PhD scholar Department of Physiology, RNT Medical College and Hospital, Udaipur, 313001(Raj.), India²(Guide) Department of Physiology, RNT Medical College and Hospital, Udaipur, 313001(Raj.), India³(Co-guide) Department of Neurology, RNT Medical College and Hospital, Udaipur, 313001(Raj.), India⁴Senior Demonstrator Department of Physiology, RNT Medical College and Hospital, Udaipur, 313001(Raj.), India⁵2nd Year Junior Resident, Department of Physiology, RNT Medical College and Hospital, Udaipur, 313001(Raj.), India

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Abstract:

A seizure is defined as a transient occurrence of signs and/or symptoms accompanied by motor manifestations or may manifest by other changes in neurologic functions like sensory, cognitive or emotional events. Seizures with symptoms occur in the acute state (provoked seizure) or in epilepsy (two or more unprovoked seizure). The integrated interpretation of symptoms, EEG report and total serum creatine kinase (CK) level in interictal period (within 15 days from last attack) can compensate for clinical uncertainty between CK level and epileptic seizures before having to resort to more sophisticated and expensive investigations. To find out the association of total serum creatine kinase (CK) concentration in patients of seizures and epilepsy. Hospital based descriptive epidemiological study Cross-Sectional in design. We were included 200 patients presented with history of seizures and epilepsy from OPD and IPD of RNT Medical College and Attached Group of Hospital, Udaipur (Rajasthan) between age of 18-65 years (both genders). Exclusion Criteria: (i) those patients who has current medical history other than seizures and epilepsy, (ii) history of smoking, (iii) patients on medication other than antiepileptics and (iv) those patients who were not willing participate in study. In present study we were taken the history of disease duration, seizure frequency per month, duration of attack in minutes and EEG (Electroencephalogram) were performed by MPEG-4, Allengers Global Health care system, India. The total creatine kinase was performed by Creatine Phosphokinase-N Acetyl Cysteine (CK-NAC) reagent test, which is standardized to the International Federation of Clinical Chemistry (IFCC) by RXL dimension. In result the mean CK-NAC rise in patients from normal limits (20-200U/L to 279.7±166.8) in mean interictal duration of 4.38±2.8 days from last attack. Male patients of seizures and epilepsy were shown greater frequency of disease and higher CK-NAC level as compare to female patients (Male 283.2±174.5, 56.5%, female 275.2±157.1, 43.5% p=0.74) and maximum level of CK-NAC was reported in between age of 35-45 years (314.1±149.2) with mean age of 33.02±13.19 years. The CK-NAC level was significantly increased in patients presented with longer history of disease (1st time 163.4±114.8U/L to by birth 476.5±166.9U/L, p-value<0.001) and higher frequency of seizure per month (1st time 164.8±112.4U/L to 11-20 / month 342.3±194.2U/L, p-value<0.001). In conclusion the elevation of serum CK-NAC than its absolute level related to the intensity of muscular activity in patients, it shows an association between them. Therefore, an increase in creatine kinase, may be used to confirm a diagnosis and also help to predict onset of next seizure and epilepsy when the entire picture was considered in our study.

Keywords: Creatine Kinase, Electroencephalogram, Creatine Phosphokinase-N Acetyl Cysteine & International Federation of Clinical Chemistry.

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Introduction

A seizure is defined as a transient occurrence of signs and/or symptoms accompanied by motor manifestations or may manifest by other changes in neurologic functions like sensory, cognitive or emotional events. Seizures with symptoms occur in the acute state (provoked seizure) or in epilepsy

(two or more unprovoked seizure). [1] From ancient time of Hippocrates to 20th century patients presented with seizures and epilepsy are emancipated as social taboo of religious superstitions such as the divine punishment or possession. These predispositions contribute to

create a greater burden than the disease itself by serious challenges of psychosocial perception/myths, emotional/ behavioural (E/B) problem, source of discrimination, encompassing quality of life in education, employment, marriage, child bearing and accrual of social benefits/ ostracisation to patients and their family members.[2]

The prevalence rate of disease in India is 2.5-11.9 per 1,000 population per year, which increase by incidence of 0.28-0.53 per 1,000 population per year [3] and the prevalence rate in Rajasthan is 3.0 per 1,000 population per year. [4]

Epileptic seizures can begin in any person at any age group. It is more common in young children and in people older than age 55 but the cause is undetermined for about half of all individuals with epilepsy, regardless of age. Children may be born with birth defects in their brain or they may suffer a head injury or infection that causes epilepsy. Traumatic head injury is the most commonly known cause in young adults. For middle-age individual's strokes, tumours and injuries are more frequent catalysts including metabolic dysfunction and immune disorders. In people age 65 and older, stroke is the most commonly known cause, followed by degenerative conditions such as Alzheimer's disease. [5]

Seizure or epilepsy may link with inflammation, the metabolic situation of clinical status and prompting factors (tumour, injury, genetic etc.) Present study focused on the role metabolic changes due to muscular activity and its mechanisms in the seizure and epilepsy. [6] Creatine kinase is thought to play an important role in the metabolism of cellular energy. It is usually found in great concentrations in metabolically active cells like skeletal muscles and neurons, [7] which release at the time of seizure and may persist few days after the seizure.

The current study was aimed to find out the association of serum CK-NAC concentration in patients of seizure and epilepsy or with normal concentration. Which help to discriminate types of various seizures in turn used as an inductive marker to confirm the diagnosis and to predict the next onset of seizure. It also helps to develop altering remedy for the creation of precise new drugs treatment methodologies.

Methodology

Present study was conducted on 200 patients presented with history of seizures and epilepsy from OPD and IPD attending EEG laboratory of Neurology department RNT Medical College and Attached Group of Hospital, Udaipur (Rajasthan). We were included both sexes in between the age of 18-65 years from February 2023 to July 2023 after approval from IRB, ethical committee and

Research Board Rajasthan university (No.RNT/ACAD./IEC/2022/288, Dated:-13.09.2022). Current study was hospital based descriptive epidemiological study Cross-Sectional in design. **a) Inclusion Criteria:**(i) Those patients who were diagnosed with seizure and epilepsy and not taking any medications other antiepileptics (ii) No intramuscularly injections were administered and there was no previous history of neuromuscular disease in any patient (iii) Written consent was obtained from the subjects and their attenders at the time of data collection. **b) Exclusion Criteria:** (i) Patients having history of diabetes mellitus and hypertension. (ii) Patients who were alcoholics and active smokers of bidi/cigarette. (iii) Those patients who had history of medical disease such as myocardial infarction, Percutaneous Coronary Intervention (PCI). (iv) Patients with clinical signs of autonomic dysfunction. (v) Patients had history of recurrent infections, muscle injuries, allergic reactions or having any recent acute infection. (vi) Pregnant women, lactating mothers, PCOD and PCOS patients and patients ingesting synthetic oral contraceptive pills (OCP). (vii) Those patients who were not willing to participate and had not given inform consent for study.

Procedure: In present study firstly, we were taken clinical history of signs and symptoms, history of disease duration, frequency of seizure and attack duration of seizure followed by video EEG of 20mins by MPEG-4, Allengers Global Health care system, India during interictal period of 15 days from the last attack of a seizure. [8]

The 2ml Venous blood has been collected from the antecubital fossa using 21G sterile needle syringes under aseptic conditions and separately transferred into plan vials and sent the sample to biochemistry laboratory of Maharana Bhopal hospital (under central lab) for determination of the CK by Creatine Phosphokinase-N Acetyl Cysteine (CK-NAC) reagent test, which is standardized to the International Federation of Clinical Chemistry (IFCC) by RXL dimension within 2 hours. [9]

For healthy people, according to Klein et al.: [10]

CKI- Women 39-308 U/L, Men 26-192 U/L

Consensus values: [11, 12]

CK-NAC: Men <190U/L (25-200U/L), Women <170 (25-170U/L)

Statistical Analysis: Statistical evaluation was done by using statistical software SPSS version 24. Results of Quantitative variables were presented as the Mean \pm Standard Deviation (SD) analyzed with independent Student's t-test (for less than two sample) and ANOVA (more than two samples). Categorical variables (qualitative data) were expressed as counts and percentages and analyzed with Chi-square test. Correlations between different

quantitative variables were performed with two-tailed Pearson's correlation analysis. For all the tests, a significant level of statistics was considered when p value was less than 0.05 and highly significant were $p < 0.001$.

Results

Table 1: CK-NAC in patient's seizure and epilepsy.

Inflammatory markers	Normal Range	Patients range	Patients mean
CK-NAC (U/L)	20-200	67-856 (116 patients, 58% >200U/L)	279.7±166.8

Out of 200 patients of present study, 87 (43.5%) was female and 113 (56.5%) were male patients with mean age of 33.02 ± 13.19 years (Table: -2).

Table:2 Demographic presentation of patients.

Gender	No. of Patients	Frequency (%)	Mean age (years)
Female	87	43.5	33.02±13.19
Male	113	56.5	
Total	200	100	

The age limit in all females was 18 to 65 years. Male patients of seizures and epilepsy were shown greater frequency towards disease. The mean interictal duration was obtained 4.38 ± 2.8 days for all cases.

There was no significant difference in CK-NAC among both the genders. However, male patients of

seizures and epilepsy were shown higher CK level as compare to female patients (male: 283.2 ± 174.5 & female: 275.2 ± 157.1 , $p = 0.74$) and maximum level of CK was reported in between age of 35-45 years (314.1 ± 149.2) without significant difference ($p = 0.163$) between different age groups (Table: -3,4).

Table:3 Gender wise mean concentration of CK-NAC in patients.

Gender	Female	Male	P Value
	Mean±S.D.	Mean±S.D.	
CKNAC (U/L)	275.2 ± 157.1	283.2 ± 174.5	0.74

Table4: Mean serum level of CK-NAC in different age groups of patients.

Age wise Distribution	18-25 Year	26-35 Year	36-45 Year	46-55 Year	>55 Year	P Value
CKNAC (U/L)	271.6 ± 160.9	298.9 ± 165.0	314.1 ± 149.2	284.4 ± 174.3	197.3 ± 200.7	0.163

On applying ANOVA, we found a significant difference between the levels of CK among different types of diagnosis. 18 (9%) patients of Epilepsy other than GME (EP), 17 (8%) patients with recurrent generalized myoclonic (GME), 81 (41%) patient's single onset generalized tonic-clonic seizure (GTCS) and 84 (42%) patients unclassified

seizure disorder (SD) were obtained with CK-NAC level of 424.4 ± 185.2 U/L, 374.9 ± 128.9 U/L, 286.7 ± 158.4 U/L & 222.8 ± 150.3 U/L. However, higher serum concentration had reported in patients of epilepsy followed by GME, GTCS and seizure disorder respectively with $**p < 0.001$ (Table: -5).

Table 5: Concentration of CK-NAC in different type of seizure and epilepsy.

Diagnosis	EP (18 patients, 9%)	GME (17 patients, 8%)	GTCS (81 patients, 41%)	SD (84 patients, 42%)	P Value
CKNAC (U/L)	424.4 ± 185.2	374.9 ± 128.9	286.7 ± 158.4	222.8 ± 150.3	<0.001**

**P-value <0.001

Total creatine kinase was 163.4 ± 114.8 U/L within duration of 1 month, 476.5 ± 166.9 U/L those patients who were suffered from disease since birth, 204.6 ± 130.9 U/L in disease duration of 1-12 months, 283.1 ± 148.6 U/L where duration of

disease 24-60 months, 344.3 ± 157.1 U/L in disease duration of 72-120 months, 395.7 ± 143.5 U/L in duration 132-240 months, 416.3 ± 82.6 U/L when history disease duration more than 240 months with p value less than 0.001** (Table:-6).

Table 6: Serum level of CK-NAC with duration of disease.

Duration of disease	within a month	1-12 Month	24-60 month	72-120 Month	132-240 month	>240 Month	By Birth	P Value
CKNAC (U/L)	163.4±114.8	204.6±130.9	283.1±148.6	344.3±157.1	395.7±143.5	416.3±82.6	476.5±166.9	<0.001**

**P-value <0.001

Total creatine kinase (279.7±166.8U/L) inpatients of seizure and epilepsy according to frequency of attack per month had 164.8±112.4U/L in patients who had expressed 1st episode of attack, 305.0±173.1U/L when patient describe 1-2 episodes of attack per month, 299.9±145.8U/L had reported

with 3-5 episodes of attack per month, 205.6±182.7U/L where 6-12 episodes of attack per month had identified and 342.3±194.2U/L where frequency of attack had 11-20 times per month (p value of <0.001**)(Table:-7).

Table 7: CK-NAC concentration with frequency of seizure attack per month.

Frequency of attack/month	CKNAC (U/L)
1st time (29patients)	164.8±112.4
1-2 times / Month (82patients)	305.0±173.1
3-5 times / Month (63patients)	299.9±145.8
6-10 times / Month (12patients)	205.6±182.7
11-20 / Month (14patients)	342.3±194.2
P value	<0.001**

**P-value <0.001

CK-NAC level was significantly increased in patients with longer history of seizures (1st time 163.4±114.8U/L to by birth 476.5±166.9U/L, P-value<0.001) and higher frequency per month (1st time 164.8±112.4U/L to 11-20 / Month 342.3±194.2U/L, P-value<0.001**).

The total creatine kinase was insignificant (p>0.05) in present study according to duration of attack in minutes had 282.3±170.6U/L with attack duration of <= 5 mins and 277.4±164.2U/L in patients where history of attack had explained for more than 5 mins (p value of 0.836) (Table: -8).

Table8: Serum level of CK-NAC to duration of seizure attack.

Duration of attack in	<= 5 minutes		>5 minutes		Total		P value
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	
CKNAC U/L	282.3	170.6	277.4	164.2	279.7	166.8	0.836

Serum CK-NAC level shows a positive correlation to frequency of seizure/month and duration of disease with correlation coefficient value (r) 0.112 and 0.444*. while negative correlation was obtained between CK-NAC and interictal duration with coefficient value of -0.062. CK-NAC level

was highly significant to duration of disease (**p=0.000). But relationship was not significant between CK-NAC and interictal duration or frequency of seizure/month (p=0.383 & 0.115)(Table: -9).

Table9: Co-relation of CK-NAC with clinical factors.

	Interictal Duration	Frequency of Seizure/ month	Duration Disease
CK-NAC (U/L)	Pearson Correlation	-0.062	0.112
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.383	0.115

**P-value <0.001

Discussion

There was less information obtained from literature review, which revealed the combination of serum

CK as markers for differentiating epileptic seizures. Therefore, present study analysed the role of serum CK as a CK-NAC in all aspects of seizure and epilepsy.

In present study concentration of CK-NAC in serum ranges from 67-856U/L (normal range 20-200U/L) with mean of 279.7 ± 166.8 U/L. It shows that the mean serum CK-NAC level was elevated in patients from normal. This may be due to increased release of CK-MM isoenzyme in skeletal muscles during epileptic seizure. The muscular contractions due to seizures possibly cause changes in the sarcolemma, which persist for 3–8 days and lead to the release of creatine kinase into the extracellular space. Its increase depends on the extent and intensity of muscle contractions. (Chesson AL et al. (1983)). [13]

In similar aspect of present study Ijaz F et al. (2020) reported higher CK-NAC level in the epileptic group as compare to the pseudo-seizure groups as well as to control group (mean serum CPK in the epileptic group was 257.7 ± 24.6 IU/100 ml, in pseudo-seizure groups was 130.1 ± 74.3 IU/100 ml and in the control group was 79.9 ± 27.7 IU/100 ml). [14]

In Support of our results Neufeld MY et al. (1997) found the significant rise in serum CK level of at least 15 U/L on the 2nd day of seizures, that is highly indicative marker for a generalised epileptic event, even when sequential tests were within the normal range. [15]

Similarly, in study of Glötzner Privatdozent F. L. et al. (1979) the elevated level of CK-NAC was obtained in generalized seizures patients, that reaches at maximum level after 40 hours of seizure then slowly normalize. [16]

In present study serum CK-NAC level was insignificant among both the genders and with different age groups of the patients. In similarity of this Erkan Goksu et al. (2009) reported non-significant difference in CK-NAC level between various age groups and both the genders of seizure patients. [17]

In contrast to present study Nass R D et al. (2017) obtained significantly elevated CK level more frequently in males in comparison to females (65.3% in males, 51.2% in females, $p = 0.041$). This may be due direct and indirect role of oestrogen hormone to maintain CK-NAC level in females. [18]

In present study serum level of CK-NAC was significantly ($P < 0.001$) altered in different types of seizure and epilepsy. The mean CK-NAC was elevated in all types of seizures than its absolute level. Moreover, in patients of generalised epilepsy this increase was more than twice from normal. In analogue to present findings Brigo F et al. (2105) reported significantly higher CK levels in patients with epileptic seizure ($p < 0.5$, all types) and maximumly raised in patients of generalised epilepsy. While, in contrast to present study Javali

M et al. (2017) shows no- relation between raised serum CK-NAC and type of seizure. [19,20]

In present study CK-NAC was significantly ($p < 0.001$) altered with duration of disease and frequency of attack. While, the change was insignificant with duration of attack. Increased level of CK-NAC obtained in longer duration of disease (163.4 ± 114.8 to 476.5 ± 166.9) and higher frequency of seizure per month (164.8 ± 112.4 to 342.3 ± 194.2), as greater number of seizures for longer duration of disease in patients increases the intensity of muscular contraction and release's higher amount of CK-NAC. Our results are similar to results of Chesson A et al. (1980) study, who reported that the CK-NAC was significantly elevated ($p < 0.05$) in GTCS patients with longer duration of disease and greater series of seizure. But elevation of CK was not prerequisite with duration of attack and injuries of patients. [21]

While, in contrary to present study Wyllie E et al. (1985) found that the multiple seizures in patients were not responsible for increased CK level, but there was a clear trend of higher CK in injured patients with series of seizure attack. [22]

Serum CK-NAC level shows a positive correlation to frequency of seizure/month and duration of disease. While, the negative correlation was obtained between CK-NAC and interictal duration. CK-NAC level was statistically significant to duration of disease ($p = 0.000$). But relationship was not significant between CK-NAC, interictal duration and frequency of seizure/month ($p = 0.383$ & 0.115). This clearly indicate that duration of disease was mainly responsible for increased serum CK-NAC in patient's seizure and epilepsy (Javali M et al. (2017)). [20]

Our Study shows that CK plays a major role in energy generation in skeletal muscle by catalysing the transphosphorylation of phosphate from creatine phosphate to adenosine-diphosphate producing adenosine-triphosphate (ATP). The ATP thus formed is used to phosphorylate glucose for muscular contraction is catalyzed by hexokinase and the resulting glucose-6-phosphate which oxidized by glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase, with this simultaneous reduction of nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADP) is seen. The change in absorbance at 340 nm due to the formation of NADP is directly proportional to the CK. CK is rapidly inactivated by oxidation of the sulfhydryl groups in the active centre. The CK enzyme can be reactivated by the addition of N-acetylcysteine (NAC) (Javali M et al. (2019)). Creatine kinase may also be involved in an "energy shuttle" shifting ATP from the mitochondrial matrix to the cytoplasm through a direct link between the CK-PCr system of cell and induce Ca^{2+} -flux. Which regulate the excitation and

relaxation phases of muscle, that can be used to predict the intense muscular activity or next onset of seizure in patients (Wallimann T et al. (2011)). [20,23,24]

Summary and Conclusion

Interictally elevation of serum CK as a CK-NAC than its absolute level appears to be a more sensitive indicator of epileptic seizures. Present study shows maximum CK-NAC level in patients of generalized epilepsy, with longer duration of disease and higher frequency of seizure may be due to the intense muscular contractions by seizures patients. Muscular activity possibly causes changes in the sarcolemma, which persist for 3–8 days and lead to the release of creatine kinase into the extracellular space. Therefore, an increase in creatine kinase, may be used to confirm the diagnosis and to predict the next onset of seizure and epilepsy, when the entire picture was considered in our study. It also helps to develop altering remedy for the creation of precise new drugs treatment methodologies.

Ethics approval and consent to participate:

Present study was hospital based descriptive epidemiological study Cross-Sectional in design conducted after approval from IRB, ethical committee and Research Board Rajasthan university (No.RNT/ACAD./IEC/2022/288, Dated on 13.09.2022. Subjects were recruited with written consent.

List of abbreviations: -CK, EEG, CK-NAC, IFCC, EP, GME, GTCS & SD.

Conflict of Interest- No conflict of Interest

Authors Contribution-

SC- Study design, definition of intellectual content, literature search, Statistical analysis, manuscript preparation and manuscript, review and editing.

TR- Data collection and EEG interpretation

AC- Literature Search and Statistical analysis

PK- - Literature Search and Statistical analysis

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